

INTRODUCTION. Latin is considered an international language from the point of view of medical terminology. It is used to study clinical diseases such as physical symptoms, disturbances or changes. In this we are going to look at few examples of clinical terminologies. There is hardly any other aspect of medicine that is so discouraging for the beginning student as medical terminology. Although medical terms have been drawn from many languages, a large majority are from Greek and Latin. Some familiarity with the meaning of the most frequently used roots, prefixes, and suffixes will clarify the whole field. With a little study, it will be found that the long and formidable sounding medical terms are a combination of words, which describe parts of the body, a function, or a condition. The basic terms occur repeatedly in various combinations. A knowledge of the meaning of the roots, prefixes, and suffixes enables the student to analyse the medical terms into component parts. This is of the greatest aid in learning to understand the vocabulary of medicine. Some names of diseases given by the ancients and still used to-day are, in many instances, simply descriptions of the outstanding symptoms; for example, hydro-phobia-fear of water-for rabies, because the inability to drink is an early, characteristic sign of the disease.

Greek and Latin Origins. As a language, English is historically and culturally linked with Latin. Long before English became the *lingua franca* of science and medicine, it was Latin that dominated. Before the 3rd century, medical students also received instructions in Greek. In fact, both Greek and Latin shaped the conventions of medical as well as scientific writing for over 2,000 years.

Ancient Greek society valued and encouraged literary pursuits as much as mathematical and scientific studies. So, it should come as no surprise that Greek doctors particularly excelled at diagnostics—the field that, no doubt, benefits from one’s imaginative depth and penchant for figurative thinking.

For example, the Greek term *diabetes mellitus* literally means “flowing through/sweet as honey,” which, most probably, initially referred to the sweet odor of the urine of a person with diabetes. The terminology for medical conditions that was developed by Greek doctors continues to be the basis of our classifications of diseases.

Prefixation, i.e. the addition of a prefixal morpheme (prefix) to the root, does not change its meaning, but only adds to this meaning some component indicating localization (above, below, in front, behind), direction (approaching, moving away), flow in time (before something, after something), on the absence or denial of something.

Prefixes developed primarily from prepositions, so their direct meanings coincide with the meanings of the corresponding prepositions.

Some prefixes, based on direct meanings, have developed secondary, figurative ones. Thus, the Greek preposition-prefix *para-* (“near, nearby”) developed a figurative meaning “retreat, deviation from something, discrepancy between the external manifestations of the essence of a given phenomenon”: for example, *para-nasalis* - paranasal, but *para-mnesia* (Greek

mnesis – “memory”) – paramnesia – a general name for distortions of memories and memory deceptions.

Romans happily inherited Greeks’ treasure-trove of medical knowledge, which they carefully preserved through translation into Latin and propagated among their numerous vassals. A huge medical encyclopedia called *De Medicina* (About Medicine), written by the Roman nobleman Cornelius Celsus, recorded all that was then known about Greek and Roman medicine.

Word Formation. As mentioned before, Greek doctors were particularly skillful diagnosticians. For this reason, Greek terms often occur in clinical terminology, e.g., cardiology, nephropathy, gastritis, whereas Latin words make up most anatomical terms: e.g., cor, ren, or ventriculus. Greek is a great source of specialized terminology thanks to its linguistic malleability, namely, its amazing suitability for building compound words. When the rapid expansion of medical science during the last two centuries required a stock of new terms for the newly discovered diseases and the invented medical tools, Greek words, often in their Latinized forms, became the way to go.

In fact, almost a half of the widely used medical terminology, although based on Greek and Latin, is less than one-century-old. Table 1 below shows some words for organs or parts of human body in Greek paired with the common medical conditions and human organs in plain English: Table 1. Organs or parts of human body associated with nominal terms

Prefixes of position describe a place, location, or position in the body. Prefixes of number and measurement describe an amount, size, or degree of involvement. Prefixes of direction indicate a pathway or route. Here are few examples

Anti: against

Epi : above

Dys: disturbance of function

Dia: across

Endo : inside

Hypo: below normal or below

Peri: covering

Syn : joining , adhesion

Scores of simple Gr. root words are used in our every-day English without our realizing their origin. To quote just a few: acme, basis, chaos, character, criterion, dogma, drama, echo, enigma, horizon, phantasia, stigma, thema, etc. aden-gland aorta-bronchos-gullet chole-bile derma-skin gastEr-belly haima-blood hepar-liver hygieia-health hymen-membrane kardia-heart kephal&-head. kranion-skull larynx-voice box mania-madness, frenzy nausea-seasickness neuron-tendon, nerve osteon-bone ophthalmos-eye pepsis-digestion pharmakon-drug pharynx-throat pleura-side, rib.

Suffixation is the addition of a suffix to a generating (motivating) stem. The derivative obtained in this way is called suffixal. Suffixes perform an important classifying function.

Thanks to them, words are correlated with the corresponding classes of concepts: for example, all nouns with the suffixes -ul(-cul-), -ol belong to the class of so-called deminutives - words with a diminutive meaning (lobulus - “lobule”, tuberculum - “tubercle” , foveola - “dimple”).

Verbal (derived from the verb stem) nouns with the suffix -io express the general categorical meaning of “process”, “action” (flexio – “bending”, rotatio – “rotation”, curatio – “treatment”). Verbal nouns with the suffix -or have a general categorical meaning of “a tool, an instrument with which an action is performed” or “a person who performs an action” (m. flexor -

flexor muscle, i.e. rotator - rotating muscle, prosector - prosector - "one who cuts ": the person performing the autopsy).

It is difficult to overestimate the classifying function of the term element-suffix, which correlates words with a specific terminological concept. Thus, all nouns with the suffix -itis express the general terminological concept of "inflammatory disease, inflammation."

A suffix always exists only in a bound form, that is, as part of a derivative. For example, the suffix -itis only in combination with a productive stem acquires the above meaning, while the Latin inflammatio is an independent word meaning "inflammation".

Suffixes generally categorized as (i) surgical, (ii) diagnostic, pathological, and related, and (iii) grammatical (adjectival, noun, plural) suffixes terms *cardiorrhexis* (above) and *cardiorrhaphy* (below) have different suffixes: -*rrhexis* is a diagnostic suffix and -*rrhaphy* is a surgical suffix:

Grouping the surgical, diagnostic, pathological, related, and grammatical suffixes makes them easier to remember them. *Surgical* suffixes describe a type of invasive procedure performed on a body part. *Diagnostic* suffixes describe a procedure performed to identify the cause and nature of an illness. *Pathological* suffixes describe an abnormal condition or disease.

Exercises related to clinical terminologies:

Typhilitis: inflammation of cecum

Cervicitis: inflammation of cervix

Hysterocelectomy: surgical removal of uterus and cervix .

Haemolysis: breakdown of rbc

Azotaemia: increase level of nitrogen in blood

Gastrocele: a herniation or protrusion of meninges

Toxaemia : presence of toxins in blood

Omphalitis: inflammation of umbilical cord

Anaesthesia : loss of sensation or feeling

Dermographia : condition where rubbing causes redness of skin.

Phlebosclerosis : enlargement of veins

Conclusion. In the end its necessary to remember all the rules required to study and understand the clinical terminologies. It's important to study suffixes , prefixes , compound characters.

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